

Clinical Pattern of Stroke and Distributions According to Age, Gender and Potential Risk Factors

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Abstract

Background: Stroke with mortality rate up to 25% is a fatal clinical syndrome. Most common risk factors are Hypertension, smoking, family history of stroke and diabetes mellitus. The objective was to study the pattern of brain strokes, areas and vascular territories of brain affected as per computerized tomography scan (CT scan) findings and risk factors in stroke patients admitted in Allied hospitals of Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Allied hospitals of Rawalpindi Medical College (RMC), Rawalpindi from September 2016 to February 2017 after taking ethical approval from Institutional Research Forum (IRF). All diagnosed cases of Stroke (Ischemic stroke or Hemorrhagic stroke) on the basis of Computerized Tomography Scan (CT-Scan) or Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) admitted to Medical Units of Allied Hospitals of RMC were included in the study irrespective of their age and gender. A Structured Questionnaire designed according to the objectives of this study was used for data collection. SPSS (Version-22) for windows was used for analysis through frequencies, percentages and cross tabulations.

Result: Out of 200 diagnosed cases of stroke 115 (57.5%) were males and 85 (42.5%) were females. Mean age of patients was 53.73 years. Regarding the types of stroke, predominance of ischemic stroke 121 (60.5%) was seen as compared to hemorrhagic stroke which constitutes of 73 (36.5%) of the cases and the remaining 6 (3%) were the cases where both types of stroke were diagnosed based on CT scan reports. Male predominance 66 (54.54%) was seen in Ischemic stroke as well as in Hemorrhagic stroke 48

(65.75%) as compared to females (Ischemic stroke 55 (45.50%) and Hemorrhagic stroke 25 (34.24%).

Most common vascular territory involved in all types of stroke was of middle cerebral artery 115 (57.5%). Among Hemorrhagic stroke subarachnoid hemorrhage 49 (67.1%) was the most common site.

In our study most common potential risk factors were Hypertension 115 (57.5%), Smoking 91 (45.5%), Family history of stroke 60 (33 %) and Diabetes 55 (27.5%).

Conclusion: Most commonly ischemic stroke, with overall male predominance was seen in our study. Hypertension, smoking and diabetes were the most common modifiable risk factors. Vascular territory of Middle cerebral artery and subarachnoid area were most commonly involved regions of brain in stroke. More than 63 % of patients were above the age of 45 years.

Key words: Stroke, Ischemic Stroke, Hemorrhagic Stroke, Hypertension, Smoking, Diabetes, Risk Factors, CT-Scan, Cerebrovascular Stroke.

Introduction

Stroke is defined as a focal neurological deficit (dysphasia, hemiplegia/hemiparesis, cranial nerve palsies or hemianopia) of sudden onset that persists beyond 24 hours; and imaging technique (neuro-imaging) indicating the presence of hemorrhage or infarction, with no obvious cause other than vascular origin.¹ Ischemic strokes constitutes about 85 % percent of all strokes and 15% strokes are due to hemorrhage (sub-arachnoid and intra-cerebral).²

The pathology of (ischemic) stroke is the inability to maintain the brain homeostatic neurological deficit. Lack or low oxygen concentration (hypoxia) leads to decreased ATP

production which further causes influx of sodium ions into the cells (cytotoxic edema) and this results into the production and excretion of glutamate and then as a result membrane channels open allowing influx of calcium and sodium ions into the cells. The neuron wastage is worsened by the production of lactic acid anaerobically and low PH. Intracellular enzymes activated by calcium complete the destructive process. Hemorrhagic stroke includes the expulsive entry of blood into the parenchyma of brain and due this, the function of neurons totally ceases and fibers of white matter also split apart.³

Hypertension (HTN), smoking, alcoholism & dyslipidemia are the most common cause of stroke in the elderly, and smoking, diabetes, increased BMI, alcoholism and hypertension are significantly associated with strokes among young people.^{4,5} Other risk factors of stroke are previous stroke, transient ischemic stroke, trauma, anticoagulant use, sickle cell anemia, cocaine abuse and child birth.⁶⁻⁹

Stroke is the most important and major cause of disability in adults in the United States and Europe. In 2005 studies showed about 16 million stroke patients, who experienced it first time in life and 5.7 million deaths due to stroke, making 10% of all deaths worldwide.¹⁰⁻¹² The incidence of stroke in United States is about 795,000 annually.¹³

Though the incidence of stroke is falling in West but probably, its incidence is rising in Asia. The prevalence of stroke risk factors in Pakistan is significant and according to a study Pakistan will be the 4th most populous country in the world in terms of diabetic patients by the year 2020 and in the same way every 3rd person has hypertension who is above the age of 45 years. Most of the diagnosed patients of stroke have uncontrolled hypertension leading to increase in mortality and thus, putting a significant economic burden on the country.¹⁴ Two-third of the world load of stroke occurs in middle and lower income countries. According to the report of World Health Organization in 2002, total mortality because of stroke in Pakistan was 78,512.¹⁵ WHO estimate for year 2020 predict that after ischemic heart disease, stroke will remain the second leading cause of death, both in developed and developing countries.¹⁶

50% of strokes can be prevented just by controlling the modifiable risk factors and adjustments in lifestyle.¹⁷ Discrepancy regarding stroke risk factors, clinical features and improvement is present in patients with different age groups and genders.^{18,19}

Till now, data on the prevalence of stroke from Pakistan is deficient; however, there are various

reported case series highlighting major differences in terms of stroke risk factors, its subtypes, epidemiology and patterns. Considering a large number of population, absolute number of stroke patients in our country Pakistan would surely be in millions. Literature available on stroke and its risk factors from Pakistan indicates a very deprived condition.²⁰ Existing data does not provide any information regarding the stroke pattern and distributions according to age, gender and potential risk factors in patients admitted in Allied hospitals of Rawalpindi Medical College.

Patients and Methods

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Allied hospitals of Rawalpindi Medical University (RMU), Rawalpindi from September 2016 to February 2017 after taking ethical approval from Institutional Research Forum (IRF). All diagnosed cases of Stroke (Ischemic stroke and/or Hemorrhagic stroke) on the basis of Computerized Tomography Scan (CT-Scan) or Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) admitted to Medical Units of Allied Hospitals of RMU were included in the study irrespective of their age and gender. A Structured Questionnaire designed according to the objectives of this study was used for data collection regarding age, gender, types of stroke, vascular territories /areas of brain involved in stroke and potential risk factors of stroke in study participants. Using WHO sample size calculator our minimum required sample size calculated was 163 keeping the confidence level of 95 %, absolute precision of 7.5% and anticipated population proportion of Ischemic stroke as 52%. However, we included 200 patients in this study.²¹ Structural checklist designed for the study was used for data entry. The data was entered and analyzed in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS V.22). For all categorical variables, frequencies and percentages were calculated, whereas for all numerical variables, mean, mode, range and standard deviations were calculated. Cross tabulations were also calculated.

Results

Out of 200 diagnosed cases of stroke 115(57.5%) were males and 85(42.5%) were females (Table-I). Mean age of patients was 53.73 years with minimum age of 18 years to maximum of 90 years and 60 – 81 was the age range in which maximum numbers of stroke cases were presented.

Table I: Gender Distribution In 200 Patients Of Stroke

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	115	57.5%
Female	85	42.5
Total	200	100%

Regarding the types of stroke, predominance of ischemic stroke 121 (60.5%) was seen as compared to hemorrhagic stroke which constitutes of 73 (36.5%) of the cases and the remaining 6 (3%) were the cases where both types of stroke were diagnosed on CT scan reports. Male predominance 66 (54.54%) was seen in Ischemic stroke as well as in Hemorrhagic stroke 48 (65.75%) as compared to females (Ischemic stroke 55 (45.5%) and Hemorrhagic stroke 25 (34.24%) (Figure-I).

Figure-I: A Cluster Chart Displaying The Gender Distribution In Different Types Of Stroke.

Most common vascular territory involved in all types of stroke was of middle cerebral artery 115 (57.5%) being followed by anterior cerebral artery 42 (21%), Posterior cerebral artery 36 (18.2%) and multiple vascular territories were involved in 7 (3.5%) of the cases. Among Hemorrhagic stroke subarachnoid hemorrhage 49 (67.1%) was the most common site being followed by intra-ventricular hemorrhage 13 (17.80%) and intra-parenchymal hemorrhage 11 (15.2%).

In our study most common potential risk factor was hypertension 115 (57.5%) and the second most common risk factor was smoking 91 (45.5%), followed by family

history of stroke 60 (33%), diabetes 55(27.5%), history of transient ischemic stroke 48 (24%), recent history of child birth 25 (12.1%), trauma 6 (3%), history of anti-coagulant use 6 (3%), cocaine and alcohol abuse 0%, and sickle cell anemia 0%(Table II).

Table II: Frequency And Percentage Of Stroke Risk Factors

Risk Factors	Frequency	Percentage
Hypertension	115	57.5%
Smoking	91	45.5%
Family History of Stroke	66	33%
Diabetes	55	27.5%
History of Transient Ischemic Stroke	48	24%
Recent Child Birth	25	12.5%
Trauma	3	6%
Anti-Coagulant use	3	6%
Sickle Cell Anemia	0	0%
Cocaine/Alcohol Abuse	0	0%

Discussion

Stroke presents quite frequently in our local settings. Despite its preventable causative factors, it is affecting major fraction of our population due to negligence.²²

The mean age of patients affected by strokes in our study was 53.73 years which is consistent with Masood’s study with mean age of 54.622 years. This also shows exposure of stroke in Pakistani population at a younger age as compared to developed world, where mean age of people having stroke was 68 years in a study conducted in Japan.²³ The common age group involved in our study was 60-81 years, which is different to Vaidya’s study, where max patients age ranges from 61-70 years.²⁴

There was male dominance in our study, 57.5% were males and 42.5% were female patients, which also correlates with the study done by Vaidya(59.7% males and 40.3% females) & Mehmood (82,59% males and 41% females).^{22,24}

Regarding type of strokes, in our study predominance of ischemic stroke (60.5%) was seen as compared to hemorrhagic stroke (36.5%) with male dominance, which is consistent with the Vaidya’s study, showing 74.8% and 22.7% respectively.²⁴

The most common site of hemorrhagic stroke in our study was subarachnoid hemorrhage 67.1%, then intra-ventricular hemorrhage 17.80%, then intra-parenchymal hemorrhage 15.2%, whereas in Vaidya’s study thalamus was most common site of hemorrhage (24.7%) which is not consistent with our study,

whereas intra-ventricular hemorrhage was 17.5% which is similar to our study.²⁴ Regarding risk factors of stroke hypertension (57.5%) being the most common risk factor, followed by smoking (45.5%), family history (33%) and diabetes (27.5%), these observations are similar to previous studies, where hypertension (68% in Masood's study and 34.1% in Vaidya's study) was most common risk factor followed by smoking (27.5% in Masood's study and 14.2% in Vaidya's study).^{22,24}

Conclusion

Most commonly ischemic stroke as compared to hemorrhagic stroke with overall male predominance was seen in our study. Hypertension, smoking and diabetes were the most common modifiable risk factors. Vascular territory of Middle cerebral artery (Ischemic and hemorrhagic both) and subarachnoid area (Hemorrhagic only) were the most commonly involved regions of brain in stroke. More than 63 % of patients were above the age of 45 years. Measurements to reduce the potential risk factors may help in the prevention of stroke related problems.

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